

Towards Another Transdiscipline: Art, Science and Emancipation as a Promise and Provocation for Live Coding

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ABSTRACT

In this text I deploy Nancy Fraser’s theory of the ‘triple movement’ to analyse and re-imagine the node of technoscientific art practice, paying attention to the Mexican art context and the imagined (trans-national) community of live coding. From Fraser’s ideas, I provide an analysis of Actor-Network Theory and a general comment on technofeminism as a set of theoretical frameworks insufficient for integrating emancipation properly into artistic and scientific practices.

1 Introduction: From Double to Triple Movement

In this text I deploy Nancy Fraser’s theory of the ‘triple movement’ to analyse and re-imagine the field of technoscientific art practice in general but also applied to the particularities of the live coding practice and imagined community. I provide an analysis of Actor-Network Theory (ANT) and technofeminist philosophical frameworks with the intention to reveal ideological blindspots inherited by live coding that obscure the political dimensions of the practice and its community-building aspirations. I first take a detour to briefly explain the impact of such blindspots in a concrete community, namely the Mexican live coding scene. I then conclude this paper by applying the triple movement framework to a segment of the last chapter of the recently published Live Coding’s User Manual, hoping to supplement it with a Marxist-Feminist framework.

Double Movement (Karl Polanyi)

Figure 1: Scheme of how one might visualise Polanyi’s double movement

Fraser’s theory of the ‘triple movement’ is a response to the ideas of sociologist Karl Polanyi. In current sociological circles, Polanyi’s (2001, 1944) ‘double movement’ theory (Fig. 1) has been popularised to explain the global rise of far-right politics: as social institutions, like housing and healthcare, are commodified by the market, disembedding the economy from society, struggles to re-embed the economy in society emerge through the creation of social protection, such as subsidised social programs, labour laws, and taxes. In contemporary settings, this double movement between marketization and social protection adopts nationalistic, ethnic and/or patriarchal politics: while people move away from marketization, they produce oppressive social protection regimes (reinforcing institutions like the nation-state, the church, and the nuclear family).

For Fraser, Polanyi did not provide a deep enough analysis to avoid the oppressive nature of the re-embedding of economy in some societies, such as Stalinism and Nazism, historically, or rightwing populist movements today. This is where Fraser's intervention (2013) compensates for a blindspot of the double movement theory (Fig. 2). To avoid oppressive protection, Fraser argues that such movements should re-embed the economy in the society by taking into consideration a third dimension: emancipation. In the current political stage, an anti-pattern can be observed: movements towards emancipation are overly critical of state (oppressive) protection. The market, mimicking the grammar of emancipatory movements, co-opts them while commodifying society. Eventually when the market "crashes," hurting and upset by what they perceive as the failure of emancipatory movements (but in actuality is the market), people turn towards oppressive forms of institutional social protection. The pattern proposed by Fraser's triple movement theory is, on the one hand, recognizing the market's co-optation power by integrating a Marxist critique of capitalism into emancipatory struggles and, on the other hand, re-embedding the economy into society through emancipatory mobilisation.

Triple Movement (Nancy Fraser, 21st c.)

Figure 2: Scheme of how one might visualise Fraser's triple movement

With this framework in mind, I attempt to answer two questions in relationship to current forms of artistic and scientific transdisciplinarity tackled in the first part of this paper: what is the role of techno-scientific art and its ideologies/philosophies (like ANT, techno-feminism, etc.) in relationship to the ongoing global struggles between marketization, social protection, and emancipation? If we understand transdisciplinarity as a movement, how can we provide an emancipatory mediation between the arts and sciences that prevents the formation of both oppressive institutions as well as market-driven industries?

2 Neutral Networks

Bruno Latour, by posing a fundamental epistemological critique of the nature/culture division, has proposed a popular framework called Actor-Network Theory (ANT) broadly used in many art-science transdisciplinary nodes. Latour's claims can be understood as a form of 'double movement,' from science to art and back, that is productive since it overcomes the 'modern' bias of the nature/culture divide. The intricate web of relationships revealed by tracing the nodes necessary for scientists to claim facts makes it impossible to distinguish between what is cultural and what is natural since the mere act of observation affects the objects of the experiment. Thus, culture and nature are always intertwined. As this network is traced, we discover that mediation is salient, which resonates with the third dimension fundamental in the triple movement theory. The significant difference is that mediation in Latour is neutral and always leads to further mediations recursively and ad infinitum.

Drawing from Lossin (2022), it is possible to claim that such a web of relations, portrayed by ANT, has common aspects with the Marxist concept of commodity. A commodity could be understood as a blackbox that obfuscates the social relationships that make that thing possible - including non-human components; like prime matter or machines alongside abstractions such as the labour of people. In this way, capitalism as a system of, on the one hand, expropriation and exploitation, and, on the other, accumulation and hoarding is invisibilised. Latour's network of neutral, infinite connections does not need further political explanations. But Marx's definition of commodity is anything but neutral, it reveals how it works to marketise life and labour. One could argue that the neutral connections of ANT are indeed emancipatory as they respond to liberalism. However, Latour insists on the neutrality of the mediations, and it can be argued that liberalism is a failed political project that rather oppresses as many as it emancipates. Regardless of the usefulness of ANT to explain webs of technical mediations, it fails as a political framework precisely because the mediations of the network are actively conceptualised as politically neutral.

What can we draw from the triple movement theory to re-conceptualise transdisciplinary networks? For a political understanding of networks, Marxist, feminist, antifascist, and decolonial mediations can help us see how networks perpetuate an invisibilised market or an oppressive institution: in the case of the art-science node, the industry (either the art market or the techno-industrial complex), on the one hand, and academic traditions (like post-positivist scientificism and/or white Eurocentric art traditions), on the other hand.

3 From Neutral to Monist Mediations

Differently from ANT, technofeminism acts as a (monist) emancipatory mediation between market and society. However, because of technofeminism's roots in post-materiality, it lacks the historical-materialist, class critique necessary to avoid being captured by market forces. I will summarise Cotter's (2020) Marxist-feminist critique of post-materialist forms of feminism in four bullet points:

- Transhumanist, post-materialist ontologies are a culturalisation of neoliberalism.
- Object-oriented feminism naturalises and ontologises exchange relations common to capitalist spheres.
- New-materialist feminism argues for the 'endurance of pain and hardship' and 'expressing positive affect' within capitalism, monist feminism (Braidotti, 2013)
- Thus, increasing women-worker's endurance to high-performance productivity (therefore maximised exploitation).

In contrast, Marxist-Feminist interest 'in material reality' and in the 'economic' is not to reify capitalism but to abolish economic exploitation, to transform social reality, not the production of tools to navigate capitalism. Technofeminism is rooted in a set of emancipatory theories that are susceptible to marketization. Of course, this does not mean that technofeminism cannot indeed be liberatory under certain conditions, but it means that, feminism, or any other emancipatory theoretical framework, in order to protect itself from capitalism needs to integrate a Marxist critique. As Fraser argues, the pressing task for feminism today is "reconnecting struggles against personalized subjection to the critique of a capitalist system that while promising liberation actually imposes a new mode of domination" (Fraser, 2013: 305).

The science-art practice offered by Latour (and via Latourian frameworks) falls back into the loop of marketization and oppressive protection described by Polanyi. Technofeminism depures feminism from class struggle avoiding oppressive protection but deepening marketization. Therefore, if technoscientific art produces only positive invention and unambiguously neglects the power of critique, with a particular emphasis on class consciousness, it will remain a force that runs the risk of multiplying and disseminating neoliberal subjectivity and techno-feudal dominance.

4 Stateful Situations: The Case of Mexican Live Coding

In the first post-revolutionary moment (1920-30), Mexico's art (and particularly the musical) context could be characterised as uncertain, militant and experimental (Madrid, 2008); hegemony was yet to take form after being transformed (yet, unfortunately, not broken) by the revolution. Once the 'national project' was stabilised, artists became relevant figures for state management and their relationship with power changed. A handful of artists established a movement: they began their careers critical of the state (moving away from oppressive social protection) just to find themselves with nowhere to go and finally looping back to the state without the mediation of emancipatory forces capable of transforming (state) politics.

Neoliberal forces, after drastically eroding the state, decisively took power in the election fraud of 1988. The forces in favour of the old-fashion social protection, re-invigorated by democracy as emancipatory force, forfeited, but such an outcome pierced a hole in the political common sense of people (in other words, hegemony was scrambled). The neoliberal regime, hoping to appear democratic and transformative, and to gain allies in the arts, established a new relationship with the main cultural agents in the country by forming the National Council for Culture and Arts (CONACULTA) and the National Fund for Culture and Arts (FONCA). Ejea (2011) reveals that this council without councilors, and the fund it managed to distribute resources for art creation, only reifies and institutionalises a well-known power structure: where 10% of beneficiaries of the fund, a dozen of white, wealthy, old, city-dwelling Mexicans, stockpile more than 50% of the resources while the bottom 90% have to fiercely compete and 'be thankful' to get the leftovers. In later stages, FONCA can be understood as an institution that attempts to turn creators into entrepreneurs by providing seed capital for artists to 'start up' their careers.

The fragile neoliberal order broke around 2015 when power was stabilised by a combination of international factors (the 2008 economic crises and the subsequent political reconfiguration of global north countries: either their turn to liberalism or their inability to move away from neoliberalism) and national factors (rising numbers of forced disappearance,

extermination and concentration camps in the territory, feminicide, eroding living conditions for most people, etc.). This situation allowed the old forces of social protection to take power in Mexico once again. The movement towards social protection here referred is popular and left-leaning; however, it has historically and currently antagonised with relevant emancipatory movements (like Zapatismo, indigenous people, or different feminist collectives), and, in order to succeed, has traced a broad coalition and alliances with dubious actors. The character of the new regime, with its lights and shades, is difficult to define. In the context of this paper I will tackle oppressive attributes of the new regime.

So, Mexico's current political moment is marked by a crisis of hegemony that unfolds as a double movement: neoliberal predation followed by an attempt to re-embed people's livelihoods under the state's (oppressive) protection. The art context in Mexico has been re-imagined to fit such a protective attempt. As the political-economy of the arts is re-centralised, by eliminating CONACULTA and making FONCA (more explicitly) dependent on federal surveillance, several critical positions emerge from emancipatory movements. To name a few: feminisms, decolonialism, and the open-source software movement users, free software foundation enthusiasts, and all kinds of hacker cyber-communities. Adjacent to the philosophically open-source activist communities, live coding stands as an art movement that attempts at traversing community-oriented politics, computer science and art creation.

While Mexican communities that relate with open-source software principles, live coding in particular, provide infrastructure and spaces for new social bonds, resisting state-sponsored, art-creation institutions and fortifying emancipatory mobilisation, they remain vulnerable to marketization. The reason why Mexican live coding remains open to a market-oriented escape from the current crisis has a double source: the pervasiveness of state politics in tandem with the lack of Marxist class analysis normalised in the trans-national (aka the global north) academic and artistic environment. For instance, the open-source framework: open-source movements are often understood as 'politicised,' nevertheless they are politically agnostic (Coleman, 2013). Open-source licensing can help corporative interests to bypass legal frameworks to 'keep-up' with the fast pace of technological development; moreover, open-source is also used to experiment with software interfaces in a less regulated environment and, thus, open-source can be used for profit (differently from GNU Linux legal framework that prevents that explicitly).

Live coding openly embraces open-source software's ethos; it has also embraced technofeminism and ANT as frameworks from which they have 'weaved' ideological positions useful for the dissemination of live coding as a trans-national project. Papers like Di Próspero's (2014) and Hall's (2021) point towards Latourian analyses of live coding to make sense of its social aspects. Furthermore, many praxes of live coding rely heavily on technofeminist theoretical frameworks, imagery, visions, manifestos, etc. As such, it is worth interrogating the ways in which these ideological frameworks also introduce the aspects here critiqued (neutral and monist connections) into live coding when they are used as a social theory to explain its own community-building processes.

Mexican coding artists are trapped between an overly centralising nation-state that deploys art institutions with oppressive-protective mandates and trans-national art movements lacking a robust critical apparatus to suppress marketization. Plenty decolonial practices have been deployed to transform this situation. Most of them are concentrated on representation and visibility. However, decolonialism is susceptible to the market in the same way feminism or any emancipatory movement is: the lack of a Marxist perspective purifies the critiques of state domination from any serious economic critique and thus making an oxymoronic, 'tamed' capitalism tolerable by techno-scientific art ideological stances.

The sense of 'autonomy' of independent artists or their ability to draw resources from sources other than the state is understood as liberatory (since they 'escaped' the state) but capitalism is a totality that cannot be eluded. It is often the case that trans-national economic circuits stand behind artists like immense monopolies (Google, Meta, Amazon, etc.), the art market, international art fairs, niche art festivals, crypto-economies, or other wealthier and more industrialised (and unambiguously neoliberal) nation-states and their market-oriented, educational institutions.

The questions that require further research in an environment like Mexico's electronic art scene are: which artists are successful in this context— which art is recognized and rewarded with grants and prizes from the market? Can art that critiques the market flourish in this scenario? Moreover, what happens to the artists that can be integrated into neither the market nor the state apparatus? when no theoretical framework can explain the precarity or frank poverty of artists, what affects are engendered and what is the responsibility of well-established artists facing this situation? How can successful artists avoid stigmatising artists that are perceived as angry because of unequal wealth redistribution? Will the artworks of techno-scientific orientation communicate to the audience a co-opted form of emancipation? And finally, does technology in live coding settings appear as a self-serving tool for artists and researchers to build careers and to be complicit in capital accumulation?

In the next section I will attempt to produce a brief analysis of political ideas contained in the User's Manual of Live Coding using the 'triple movement' as a framework hoping to supplement the playfulness and the positive invention of live coding with mechanisms that prevent it from being captured by institutions that reproduce capitalist accumulation and/or the market logic altogether.

5 Stateless Situations: User's Manual

Recently, a user's manual for live coding (Blackwell et al., 2022) was published by MIT Press, and an experimental version of it has been unleashed in GitLab. The last chapter describes what live coding wants. In the segment 'Data Structures and Algorithms' an explicit political orientation is given to live coding while some distance is also put in place from another political framework:

“Could there be a world in which artists make the rules? Graeber contrasts the *structural violence* of bureaucratic systems with the creative freedom of the anarchist or artist. He claims that the true spirit of the Left is not to be found in a Socialist state but in the liberty of playful expression. The play of making new rules, new algorithms, and new structures is indeed a technological speech act, but one that brings into existence new kinds of social relations, as well as human-machine relations.” (Blackwell et al., 2022: 232)

Before trying to answer the question at the top of this segment, it is necessary to approach the distinction of anarchism and socialism here proposed. The first thing to notice in this fragment, when analysed via Fraser's theory of triple movement, is the implied definition of freedom and such conception as the central goal of the 'true left.' Freedom in this text is assumed to be a movement away from social protection, here understood as the 'structural violence' apparently inherent to the Socialist state. This snippet should be formulated and understood from a Deleuzian-Guattarian perspective: it calls for a playful experiment as an escape from overly codified social conventions. This process could be described as deterritorialization. According to Deleuze and Guattari (2013 - 1980), all deterritorialization is followed by a reterritorialization. In other words, the game for assemblage theory is to permanently be one step ahead of the abilities of capitalism to re-absorb the energy liberated by the lines of flight. Such processes must be faster than capitalism's digestive capabilities. Faramelli (2018), drawing from Zapatismo, has written extensively on how an accelerated race against capital can lead to madness and/or suicide; instead, he calls for a constant rate of slowness in the face of accelerationist, intense change. Thus, Faramelli proposes an amendment to the politics implicit in the work of Deleuze and Guattari via Zapatismo that mindfully prevents and resists capture. For Faramelli, deterritorialization must be slow and constant. A fundamental question for live coding is the question of slow deterritorialization. Is the playful expression of live coding slow and constant or does it participates and enables the speed of capitalism? Let me suggest to focus now on reterritorialization, which is often given very little attention.

The process of deterritorialization that the playful expression of live coding favours appears as the locus of liberation. Differently from the focus on liberation, I want to concentrate on the movements between deterritorialization and reterritorialization and understand them as a necessary feedback loop to transform social structures and processes insofar reterritorialization is mediated by emancipation. In this way, the playful expression of live coding ineluctably occurs followed and/or preceded by a form of social protection or marketization. Namely, without a triple movement in mind, it is unclear what mechanisms live coding has in place to avoid marketization. As Fraser cautions, referring to feminist movements' cooptation by neoliberal forces, “we who aim to emancipate women from gender hierarchy need to become more aware that we operate on a terrain that is also populated by marketizing forces” (Fraser, 2013: 327).

If the loop between social protection and emancipation is inescapable, perhaps the question of the commons via anarchism or socialism is inadequate. What is relevant is to orient ourselves towards the processes of emancipatory mobilization interplaying with structures of social protection regardless of an anarchist or socialist framework. If anarchist forces neglect the movement towards social protection (favouring only emancipation) or socialist forces neglect emancipation they will eventually be captured by oppressive social protection and/or by marketization. I suggest that the political potential of live coding is something yet to be explored that is irreducible to either anarchism nor socialism.

Later in this text there is a direct mention of Attali's argument of music's ability to herald transformations on modes of production:

“Live coding, in this analysis, is not simply a poetic or performative allusion to the hacking of cybernetic infrastructure. As well argued by Jacques Attali, music, through its abstract form, is able to explore and experiment with structures that are later adopted in the economic and social domains.” (Blackwell et al., 2022: 232)

It is beyond the scope of this paper to discuss the interpretation of Attali's argument by the authors of the handbook. However, it is worth staying with the notion that music can "foreshadow new social formations in a prophetic and annunciatory way" (Jameson, 1985).

If we are to take this snippet seriously; it is worth interrogating if live coding practice can anticipate post-capitalist modes of production by aligning to an anarchist spirit or perhaps points to the dialectic transformation of anarchism and socialism that make them both commensurable as political turbulence. Instead of favouring one ideological stance, live coding has the potential to transform both by acknowledging the need for dynamic political processes and structures.

Finally, taking into consideration this brief analysis I would like to tackle the question of artists as rule makers in relationship to live coding. Artistic creation in western settings has always had a space of tolerance for revolution, resistance, friction, antagonism, the novel and the other. This space is often the vanguard of artistic creation, the contemporary critical edge that allows western culture to maintain its vitality. The broader the tolerance for otherness, the deeper the crisis of imagination in the sphere of capitalism. This space is allowed to exist only if there is also a mechanism capable of metabolising such difference and novelty and transform it into yet another institution for the reproduction of capitalism (Haiven, 2018). Art (and artists) have never been autonomous from capitalism and their rule-breaking impetus is in itself an implicit rule that governs art-making practices. Furthermore, the current financialised capitalism, with the way it claims to harness creativity and the way that it transforms money into a cultural phenomenon, reflects the ideal of the artist as a rule maker. In contrast, live coding has the capacity to abolish the institution of art altogether; not by its formal innovation but by constituting a circuit of art exchange that does not rely on commodification of the artwork, as Attali suggested in the last chapter of his seminal work "Noise" (1985). If live coding anticipates a world without the commodification of art there are no artists to make rules; only people engaged with different art practices.

At the start of this section, I mentioned the experimental publication of the Live Coder's User Manual in a distributed version control platform. The implications of publishing a book in such way are many and remarkably interesting. Users can fork the book (that means, copying it and containing that copy in a repository of their own), modify it creating different branches, etc. Perhaps the most interesting feature that this technology enables is the 'pull request.' This means that anybody's modifications can be incorporated to the 'original' version of the book. Since the book is not source code and it is not compiled (to generate software) it is unclear how can a 'pull request' work in this sense. I should also add that a literal 'pull request' to a research project as broad and rich as the Live Coder's User Manual could compromise the integrity of the book's consistency and coherence. Nevertheless, the following paragraph should be considered a pull request: a playful provocation that is only possible because of live coding's enormous capability to modify programs on-the-fly.

"The true spirit of the Left is not to be found in (individualised) liberty but in collectivised emancipation, which can only fulfill its promises through a movement towards social protection where the dimensions of feminism, decolonialism, Marxism, antifascism and any other form of emancipatory movement are upheld. As material conditions sit, making new rules, new algorithms, and new structures is a technological promise and provocation of new kinds of social relations, as well as human-machine relations to come. If live coding remains open to market capture, as well as artists utilising datification, AI, and NFTs, the practice may eventually resolve towards data colonialism, crypto-fascism and techno-feudalism - forsaking the politics of emancipation, or even worse: co-opting the language of emancipation to sink us further into market society, which ultimately has no other pathway than that of radical oppression. These risks underscore the urgent need to develop the proper analytical tools to make a partition between, on the one hand, artworks driven by marketization, and, on the other hand, anti-market art practices using techno-scientific frameworks while also embracing emancipation." (XXXXXX et al., XXXX: XXX [from another timeline])

5.1 Acknowledgments

While writing this paper Teaching Assistants at McMaster University were on strike because we are 33% of the work force but only 3.7% of the pay roll. The strike ended with McMaster administration destroying any possibility for TAs to make a living wage and work in dignified conditions. I want to acknowledge the great effort of the students, workers and union members at McMaster and thank them for the fight that motivates this paper. I would like to acknowledge Sara Swerdlyk's solid academic and political praxis that has made it possible for me to change my understanding of art research.

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